

Analytical data on *A. pinnata*. De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines.

Analysis	Method ^a	Percentage ^b
Ash		20.0
Moisture		11.0
	SP	0.015
N	Kjeldahl	3.50
Mg	AA	0.60
K	Flame emission	3.8
Ca	AA	0.60
Mn	AA	0.13
Fe	AA	0.90
Zn	AA	0.01
As	AA	0.01
As	Gutzeib (UV-vis)	ND
Mo	AA	5 × 10 ⁻⁴
Hg	Flameless AA	ND
Pb	AA	ND
PO ₄	SP	0.56
SO ₄	Turbidimetric	1.40

^a SP = spectrophotocalorimetric, AA atomic absorption. ^b ND = nondetectable.

TG and DTA of azolla. A = *A. pinnata*, B = *A. microphylla*.

loss occurs. In the second, organic components are lost, followed by decarbonization and decomposition of inorganic sulfides and carbonates. The subsequent stages yield inorganic residue. The similarities in the TG-DTA curves of *A. pinnata* and *A. microphylla* indicate that the basic matrix is similar (see figure). *A. pinnata* exhibits weight losses of 12.42, 42.55, 62.13, and 78.30% in the temperature range 80-110, 210-320, 330-425, and 435-490 °C, respectively. *A. microphylla* shows 12.15, 44.93, 66.39, and 83.40% respectively in the range 75-110, 215-315,

325-420, and 440-490 °C. The exothermic peak temperatures in the DTA curve are at 287, 305, 358, and 460 °C for *A. pinnata* and 283, 310, 353,

and 460 °C for *A. microphylla*. The first and fourth peaks indicate the major decomposition process; the second and third peaks are less intense. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Response of transplanted rice to micronutrients and the residual effect on wheat

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We studied the effect of Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe sulfates on yield of transplanted rice Pratap in the 1985 wet season and yield of wheat in the 1985-86 winter season. The soil and foliar applications of the micronutrients were compared with 5 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha containing 54% moisture.

Soil was silty clay loam (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 8.3, 1.303% organic matter, EC 0.22 dS/m, cation exchange capacity 24.5 meq/100 g soil, and DTPA-extractable Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe at 0.80, 15.0, 0.18, and 15.5 mg/kg soil, respectively. FYM contained 0.45% N, 0.10% P, 0.35% K, and 40,200, 69, and 1,500 mg Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe, respectively, /kg (oven dry

basis). Treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Both crops received 80-17.4-33.3 kg NPK/ha in all treatments.

Soil and foliar applications of Zn and Cu increased rice yields significantly (see table). FYM with its micronutrients also increased rice yield significantly. Wheat yield was not significantly influenced by any treatment. □

Efficiency of complex fertilizers in a rice - rice farming system

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We evaluated four N sources in a randomized block design with four replications during the 1984 dry season (DS) and 1985 wet season (WS). Soil was lateritic sandy loam (pH 5.7, EC 0.115 dS/m, 0.680% organic carbon, 18 kg available P, and 150 kg available K/ ha. Rice variety Daya (120 d) was transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing. The recommended dose of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha was applied through complex mixtures A and B (18-7.86-5 kg NPK/100 kg mixture) produced by Hari Fertilizer Factory, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India; urea; and calcium ammonium nitrate plus P and K. N is in the form of NH₄Cl in mixture A and (NH₄)₂SO₄ in mixture B. The shortfall in N and K were adjusted with urea and muriate of potash. All P and K were applied at transplanting. Treatments received 50% N at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Grain yield was highest with N as NH₄Cl (3.8 t/ha) (see table). N as

Direct and residual effects of micronutrients on rice and wheat yields. Keonjhar, Orissa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Application method	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Rice	Wheat
Control		3.0	1.8
FYM 5 t/ha		3.2	1.9
Zn 4.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.3	1.7
Zn 0.11 mg/liter	Foliar	3.2	2.0
Mn 14.2 kg/ha	Soil	3.0	1.6
Mn 0.18 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.6
Cu 2.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.2	1.8
Cu 0.07 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.5
Fe 10 kg/ha	Soil	2.9	1.5
Fe 0.10 mg/liter	Foliar	3.0	1.8
CD (0.05)		0.1	ns